

10, and 15 cm) and gypsum (0, 5, 10, and 15 t/ha) on yield of rice and wheat. Soils of the experimental field were fine-textured, salt-affected, poorly drained (infiltration rate 1.0 cm/24 h), Typic Salorthids (Table 1).

Rice variety Jhona 349 was transplanted in the wet season and wheat variety Kalyan sona was sown in the dry season. Fertilizer was 100 kg N and 18 kg P/ha.

Sand cover 5 and 10 cm thick significantly increased rice and wheat yields (Table 2). A 15-cm sand cover reduced yields, possibly because the plot was too high for efficient irrigation. Gypsum had no effect on yields.

Table 2. Yield of rice and wheat with sand cover and applied gypsum. Bikaner, India.

Gypsum (t/ha)	Yield (t/ha) with sand cover of				Mean yield (t/ha)
	0	5 cm	10 cm	15 cm	
	<i>Rice^a</i>				
0	1.8	2.8	2.7	2.1	2.4
5.0	2.2	2.7	2.8	2.3	2.5
10.0	2.2	2.6	2.5	2.3	2.4
15.0	2.3	2.9	2.5	2.1	2.5
Mean	2.0	2.8	2.6	2.2	2.5
	<i>Wheat^b</i>				
0	1.1	1.7	1.6	1.4	1.5
5.0	1.3	2.0	1.9	1.3	1.6
10.0	1.4	1.8	1.7	1.4	1.6
15.0	1.4	1.7	1.6	1.1	1.5
Mean	1.3	1.8	1.7	1.4	1.6

^aLSD = 0.33 with sand, ns with gypsum. ^bLSD = 0.50 with sand, ns with gypsum.

Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Effect of *Sesbania bispinosa* decomposition time and sodicity on rice yield

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We evaluated the effect of *S. bispinosa* decomposition time (0, 1, and 2 wk under submerged conditions) at 4 levels of sodicity (exchangeable sodium percentage [ESP] 48, 36, 28, and 16) on N turnover and rice yield.

Soils were Aquic Natrustalfs (Table 1). Crops were irrigated with tubewell water (electrical conductivity 0.3 dS/m) as required.

The 1986-87 field experiment was a split-plot design with ESP levels in the main plots and decomposition period in the 40-m² subplots, with 4 replications.

Sesbania seeds were broadcast in 5 cm standing water at 70 kg seed/ha. Sowing was on 13, 20, and 27 May 1986, and 7, 14, and 21 May 1987. *Sesbania* was harvested at 50 d after seeding, chopped, and incorporated to allow decomposition periods of 0, 1, and 2 wk under submergence. Rice cultivar Jaya was transplanted 15 Jul 1986 and 9 Jul 1987. Submergence was maintained throughout rice growth. The rice crop

was fertilized with 150 kg N (urea), 9 kg Zn/ha. Half the N and all the Zn were applied at transplanting, the remaining

N was topdressed in 2 equal splits 3 and 6 wk after transplanting. Rice was harvested 30 Oct 1986 and 31 Oct 1987.

Grain yields were significantly improved at all ESP levels when *sesbania* had decomposed for 1 wk

Table 1. Initial soil characteristics. Karnal, India, 1986-87.

Soil no.	ESP	pH (1:2 soil: water)	EC (dS/m)	Exchangeable Ca + Mg (meq/100 g)	Organic C (%)	Active Mn (mg/kg)	Active Fe (mg/kg)	Available P (mg/kg)	Available K (mg/kg)
1	48	9.5	0.95	3.8	0.19	82	285	20	160
2	36	9.2	0.86	5.2	0.20	79	275	16	158
3	28	9.0	0.77	6.0	0.20	78	275	14	155
4	16	8.8	0.65	6.7	0.21	75	270	10	150

Table 2. Effect of sodicity and decomposition period of *S. bispinosa* on grain yield of rice, N contribution, and change in ESP. Karnal, India, 1986-87.

ESP	Decomposition period (wk)	Oven-dry biomass of <i>sesbania</i> (t/ha)		N turned (kg/ha)		Rice grain yield (t/ha)		ESP after rice harvest in 1987	
		1986	1987	1986	1987	1986	1987		
48	0	3.46	3.38	94.1	93.8	5.7	5.7	36	
	1	3.50	3.45	94.9	94.0	6.5	6.4	34	
	2	3.44	3.41	93.6	93.5	6.7	6.7	32	
36	0	3.78	3.75	102.4	100.6	6.2	6.2	26	
	1	3.85	3.85	104.3	102.2	6.7	6.7	25	
	2	3.80	3.86	103.4	101.8	6.8	6.9	25	
28	0	3.89	3.88	105.3	104.6	6.1	6.1	19	
	1	4.00	4.02	108.8	105.8	6.7	6.6	18	
	2	3.92	4.00	106.6	104.9	6.9	6.9	16	
16	0	3.90	3.95	105.7	105.9	6.2	6.2	12	
	1	3.88	3.90	105.1	106.0	6.8	6.8	10	
	2	3.99	3.98	108.1	107.5	7.0	7.0	10	
LSD (0.05)		ESP	0.16	0.15	4.5	4.2	ns	ns	—
Decomposition period			ns	ns	ns	ns	0.4	0.34	—

(Table 2). Longer than 1 wk decomposition had no significant effect. Although high ESP significantly reduced biomass turnover and N contribution of sesbania, it had no effect on yield. ESP levels were substantially reduced after harvest. □

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Physiology and plant nutrition

Influence of new terpenoid analogue of abscisic acid on chilling resistance of rice seedlings

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We studied the effect of the new terpenoid analogue of abscisic acid of the acetylene-acetate type coded LAB 173711 (see figure) on resistance to chilling in 14-d-old rice seedlings.

Seedlings were sprayed with LAB 173711, at 10^{-3} mol/liter, maintained in a glasshouse at 29/ 21 °C day/night temperature, 12 h photoperiod, and 80% relative humidity for 24 h, then transferred to a chamber at 5 °C temperature for 3 and 5 d. Recovery in the glasshouse was monitored for several days.

Survival in unprotected plants chilled for 3 d was 60% 2 d after treatment (DAT); no plants survived 5 DAT (Table 1). Plants sprayed with LAB

173711 had 100% survival. The number of plants surviving 5 °C for 5 d was similar.

The analogue also protected the root system (Table 2). The number of

adventitious roots, root length, and root weight were higher in treated plants. The stability of the root system may contribute to the increased survival rate in protected plants. The increase in chilling tolerance may also be due to the direct action of analogue 173711 on stomatal closure; that prevented water loss through transpiration. □

Table 1. Survival of rice plants treated with LAB 173711, chilled at 5 °C for 3 and 5 d, and returned to 29 °C for recovery. Data are means ± SE of 3 parallel experiments with 10 plants each.

Treatment	Survival (%) with given time at 29 °C				
	1 d	2 d	4 d	6 d	8 d
	<i>Chilled for 3 d</i>				
Control	100.0 ± 0	60.0 ± 5.8	23.33 ± 6.6	0	0
With 173711	100.0 ± 0	100.0 ± 0	100.0 ± 0	100.0 ± 0	100.0 ± 0
	<i>Chilled for 5 d</i>				
Control	100.0 ± 0	44.0 ± 3.2	0	0	0
With 173711	100.0 ± 0	74.0 ± 6.6	68.0 ± 11.1	30.0 ± 4.1	30.0 ± 4.1

Table 2. Root growth of rice plants treated with LAB 173711, chilled at 5 °C for 2 d, and returned to 29 °C for 7 d recovery.^a

Treatment	Nodal roots ^a (no./plant)	Length ^b (cm)	Fresh weight ^b (mg)	Dry weight ^b (mg)
Control	17.0 ± 1.8	9.9 ± 1.2	205.8 ± 28.3	27.7 ± 7.0
173711	26.2 ± 1.7	14.7 ± 2.2	770.8 ± 28.0	69.2 ± 7.0

^a Data are means ± SE of 5 measurements. ^b Data are means ±SE of 8 measurements.

Chemical structures of abscisic acid (ABA) and of its terpenoid analogue LAB 173711.

Crop management

Effect of planting overage seedlings on rice duration, yield, and yield attributes

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Varietal differences in growth duration are due primarily to differences in length of the vegetative phase. We studied 15 prerelease cultures and varieties in the 1983 wet season. The field experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with three replications. Due to an unprecedented severe drought, 54-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 2-3 seedlings/hill spaced 15 × 15 cm.

The maturity of short-duration varieties (95-120 d) was prolonged to